

VARIATION OF THE ABSOLUTE RATES OF MIGRATION AND TRANSPORT NUMBER OF ELECTROLYTIC IONS WITH DILUTION.

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Onsager (*Physik. Z.*, 1926, 27, 388; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 341) has deduced equations for the equivalent conductivity and ionic mobility in dilute solutions of strong electrolytes. The equations are free from arbitrary constants and the conductivities can be easily evaluated with the help of them. A limiting equation for the transport number can also be deduced from the equations of Onsager (*loc. cit.*). The conductivity equation has been found by Shedlovsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 1411) to be valid for uni-univalent electrolytes upto a concentration of about 0.0001*N*. The researches of McInnes and co-workers (*Chem. Rev.*, 1932, 11, 171) have also shown that the transport number equation holds for uni-univalent electrolytes in dilute solutions.

The absolute velocities and transport numbers of the anions of aqueous solutions of KCl, KNO₃, and K₂SO₄ have been measured at concentrations ranging between 0.04*N* and 0.001*N* by the method of moving boundaries using Mukherjee's cataphoretic tube. The results have been discussed in the light of the limiting equations of Onsager (*loc. cit.*).

T H E O R E T I C A L.

If l_c represents the mobility of an ion at a concentration C , and l_∞ , the same at infinite dilution then according to Onsager (*loc. cit.*)

$$l_c = l_\infty - \left[\frac{0.9838 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}} w l_\infty + \frac{28.95 Z_1}{(DT)^{3/2} \eta} \right] \sqrt{(Z_1 + Z_2)C} \quad \dots (i)$$

where D is the dielectric constant of the solvent, T , the temperature; Z_1 is the charge carried by the particular ion; η is the viscosity of the solvent; C is the equivalent concentration; Z_1 and Z_2 are the respective valencies of the anions and the cations:

$$w = Z_1 Z_2 \frac{2q}{1 + \sqrt{q}}; \text{ and } q = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 (l'_\infty + l''_\infty)}{(Z_1 + Z_2)(Z_2 l'_\infty + Z_1 l''_\infty)}$$

where l'_∞ and l''_∞ are the limiting mobilities of the cations and anions.

The equation may be put in a simpler form as

$$l_c = l_o - (\alpha l_o + \beta) \sqrt{C} \quad \dots \text{(ii)}$$

For uni-univalent electrolytes at 35° the equation reduces to

$$l_c = l_o - (0.168 l_o + 27.1) \sqrt{2C}.$$

For the sulphate ion in the uni-bivalent electrolyte K_2SO_4 , the relation is

$$l_c = l_o - (0.307 l_o + 54.2) \sqrt{3C}.$$

The equation for transport number deduced from the relations of Onsager is of the following form

$$\left(\frac{\partial T_+}{\partial \sqrt{C}} \right)_{C \rightarrow 0} = \frac{\beta}{\Lambda_o} \left[T_+(Z_1 + Z_2) - Z_1 \right] \sqrt{Z_1 + Z_2} \quad \dots \text{(iii)}$$

where T_+ represents the cation transference number, Λ_o , the equivalent conductivity of the electrolyte at infinite dilution and β is the constant of Onsager's equation equals to 27.1 for dilute aqueous solutions at 35°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Recrystallised potassium iodoeosinate at suitable concentrations has been used as the indicator solution. All the solutions have been prepared by direct weighing with pure conductivity water having specific conductivities lying between 1.2×10^{-6} and 1.3×10^{-6} mho (For detailed description of the procedure compare Sen-Gupta (*This issue*, p. 685).

Solvent Correction. That the transport number measurements in dilute solutions must be corrected for the conduction of the solvent impurities was first pointed out by Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2741). Longworth derived the following relation between $T_{\text{corrected}}$ and T_{observed}

$$T_{\text{cor}} = T_{\text{obs}} \left(1 + \frac{K_w}{K_s} \right) \quad \dots \text{(iv)}$$

where K_w represents the conductivity of the water used and K_s , that of the solution. The relation is only approximate since the conductivity of the solvent impurities is influenced by the electrolyte dissolved in water. No solvent correction is, however, necessary for the measured absolute velocity of ions,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

TABLE I.

Variation of the velocity and transport number of the chlorine ion in potassium chloride with dilution.

Temperature = 35°.

Salt conc.	T_{cl} .	T_{cl} (cor.) (mean).	$V_{cl} \times 10^5$.	$V_{cl} \times 10^5$ (mean).
0.04N	0.503		83.5 cm./sec.	
	0.504	0.504	83.6	83.5 cm./sec.
	0.504		83.6	
0.02N	0.502		86.4	
	0.504	0.503	86.1	86.3
0.01N	0.503		88.4	
	0.503	0.503	88.3	88.4
	0.503		88.4	
0.005N	0.503		90.0	
	0.504	0.504	90.1	90.1
	0.504		90.1	
0.002N	0.500		91.6	
	0.501	0.503	91.6	91.6
	0.500		91.6	
	0.500		91.6	
	0.500		91.7	
0.001N	0.498		92.4	
	0.500	0.504	92.4	92.4
	0.500		92.2	
	0.499		92.0	
	0.499		92.6	
			92.3	
Limit at infinite dilution	From graph	0.503	—	94.3

TABLE II.

Variation of the velocity and transport number of the nitrate ion in potassium nitrate with dilution.

Temperature = 35°.

Salt conc.	T_{NO_3}	T (cor.) (mean).	$V_{\text{NO}_3} \times 10^6$.	$V_{\text{NO}_3} \times 10^6$. (mean).
0.04N	0.481	0.481	75.0 cm./sec.	75.0 cm./sec.
0.02N	0.483	0.483	78.6	78.6
0.01N	0.484			
	0.485	0.485	81.8	
	0.485		82.0	82.0
			82.1	
0.005N	0.487		83.3	
	0.487		83.5	
	0.487	0.488	83.3	83.3
	0.488		83.3	
	0.487		83.3	
	0.488		83.5	
0.001N	0.487		86.7	
	0.487	0.490	86.3	86.3
Limit at infinite dilution	From graph	0.490		88.6

TABLE III.

Variation of the velocity and transport number of the sulphate ion in potassium sulphate with dilution.

Temperature = 35°.

Salt conc.	T_{SO_4}	T_{SO_4} (cor.) (mean).	$V_{\text{SO}_4} \times 10^6$.	$V_{\text{SO}_4} \times 10^6$. (mean).
0.04N	0.517		77.5 cm./sec.	
	0.517	0.517	77.5	77.5 cm./sec.
0.02N	0.515		81.3	
	0.516		81.4	
	0.517	0.516	81.5	81.4

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Slat conc.	TABLE III (contd.).		$V_{\text{SO}_4} \times 10^5$	$V_{\text{SO}_4} \times 10^6$
	T_{SO_4}	T_{SO_4} (cor.) (mean).		
0.02N	0.516		81.4	
	0.515		81.3	
	0.516		81.4	
0.01N	0.511		83.9	
	0.511	0.511	83.7	83.8
	0.510		83.8	
0.005N	0.504		86.8	
	0.505		86.8	
	0.504		87.0	
	0.506	0.506	87.0	87.0
	0.505		87.2	
	0.506		87.0	
	0.505		86.8	
	0.506		87.2	
0.002N	0.502		91.2	
	0.505		91.3	
	0.504	0.505	91.3	91.3
	0.504		91.2	
	0.504		91.3	
	0.505			
0.001N	0.500		93.2	
	0.501		93.0	
	0.500	0.505	93.1	93.1
	0.501		93.2	
	0.501		93.2	
	0.502			
Limit at infinite ... dilution		0.509		97.5

It will be seen that when the velocity l_e/F is plotted against $\sqrt{C}$ a straight plot is obtained up to a dilution of 0.01N in the case of the chloride and

the nitrate and up to 0.005*N* in the case of the sulphate. The deviation in concentrated solutions is very large in the case of the sulphate. The slopes of the limiting curves can be calculated from the equation of Onsager. The following table contains the calculated and the observed values.

TABLE IV.

Electrolyte.	Obs. slope $\times 10^5$.	$\frac{\alpha l_0 + \beta}{F} \times 10^5$.
KCl	60	60
KNO ₃	72	59.3
K ₂ SO ₄	147	145

Onsager and Fuoss (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2689) suggested an extrapolation of the limiting equation in the following form

$$l_c = l_0 - A\sqrt{C} + B.C \quad \dots (v)$$

where A equals $\alpha l_0 + \beta$ and B is an arbitrary constant.

$l_0 + A\sqrt{C}$ is plotted against C in order to evaluate the constant B .

TABLE V.

Conc. of the K-salt.	$l_c + A\sqrt{C}$			
	Cl (35°).	NO ₃ (35°).	SO ₄ (35°).	*NO ₃ (25°).
0.04N	92.6	84.3	107.6	68.9
0.02	91.7	85.1	98.9	69.4
0.01	91.3	85.1	95.3	69.9
0.005	91.2	84.6	94.3	70.3
0.002	91.1	...	94.5	70.6
0	91.0	85.7	94.3	71.5

FIG. 2.

From an examination of the curves (Fig. 2) it will be seen that the extrapolated equation of Onsager holds good for the case of chloride and sulphate between 0.01N and 0.04N, while the plot is irregular with the nitrate for which B has a negative value showing the peculiar character of the nitrate ion.

In Fig. 3 are plotted the cation transport numbers of KCl, KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 together with the results obtained by McInnes and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) at 25° on KCl, KNO_3 and Na_2SO_4 . The dotted curves represent the theoretical lines. It will be seen that the limiting slope is only attained in the case of the nitrate and the sulphate at the highest dilution observed.†

* Taken from the transport number data of Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1185) and the conductivity data of Shedlovsky (*loc. cit.*).

† Hartley and Donaldson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 457) have recently measured the transport numbers of certain unsymmetrical electrolytes including K_2SO_4 and observed that the limiting slope is attained in every case at the highest dilution observed by them,

S U M M A R Y.

1. The variation of the transport numbers and absolute rates of migration with dilution has been measured in case of KCl , KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 between dilution $0.04N$ and $0.001N$. In the most dilute solutions the limiting equations of Onsager have been shown to hold good.

2. Between dilutions $0.005N$ and $0.04N$ the modified equation of Onsager and Fuoss has been shown to hold for the case of the chloride ion and approximately for the sulphate but not for the nitrate.

3. In the case of the nitrate and the sulphate, the transport number curves reach the limiting slope only at the highest dilution ($0.001N$) used by the authors. In the case of chloride the transport number is almost constant within the range of experimental error.

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